

A Case Series On Unexplained Infusion Reactions Linked To Iv-Drip Sets

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ABSTRACT

Infusion-related reactions (IRRs) are adverse clinical responses occurring during or soon after the administration of intravenous (IV) drugs or fluids. Although most are attributed to pharmacological hypersensitivity, medical device-related factors can mimic drug reactions and often go unrecognized. Over five days, a tertiary care hospital recorded an unusual cluster of thirty-one infusion reactions involving diverse medications such as metronidazole, paracetamol, clindamycin, and fluids like normal saline, dextrose-saline, and Ringer's lactate. Each episode developed within 10–20 minutes of infusion initiation and was characterized by chills, rigors, and transient fever. Symptoms subsided promptly after discontinuation of the infusion and administration of intravenous chlorpheniramine (45.5 mg) and hydrocortisone (100 mg). The uniformity and close temporal grouping of reactions suggested a single external factor rather than multiple drug allergies. Investigation revealed that all affected infusions used drip sets from the same manufacturing batch. After replacing these sets with an alternative brand, the same drugs were re-infused without recurrence of symptoms, confirming the drip sets as the source. This observation emphasizes the critical role of materiovigilance in identifying device-related adverse events and differentiating them from true pharmacological reactions. Maintaining rigorous quality assurance of consumables, batch traceability, and staff awareness is essential for ensuring patient safety and preventing avoidable medical errors.

Keywords: Infusion reactions, IV set contamination, Materiovigilance, Adverse events, Device safety, Hospital surveillance.

INTRODUCTION

Intravenous (IV) infusion therapy remains integral to inpatient medical management, enabling precise and rapid delivery of therapeutic agents. However, infusion therapy is not without risks. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines an infusion-related reaction as *any untoward* sign or symptom occurring during or shortly after the administration of an intravenous pharmacological or biological substance [1]. These reactions range from mild fever and chills to severe anaphylactic-like responses, occasionally leading to hypotension, dyspnea, or shock [2].

Traditionally, clinicians attribute IRRs to drug hypersensitivity or contamination of infusion fluids. Yet, increasing reports underscore the contribution of medical devices, particularly IV drip sets, cannulas, and tubing materials, to such events [3]. Modern infusion equipment, though sterile and disposable, can still harbor endotoxins or leachable plasticizers introduced during manufacturing or improper storage [4]. These non-immunologic triggers often produce pyrogenic or pseudoallergic reactions clinically indistinguishable from true allergies [5].

In India, the Materiovigilance Programme of India (MvPI) was initiated in 2015 to systematically monitor and analyze medical device-associated

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adverse events [6]. Despite this framework, device-related infusion reactions remain underreported, as clinicians frequently ascribe them to the administered drugs. According to recent data, approximately 10–15 % of infusion-related adverse events are associated with device contamination or manufacturing defects [7].

The present case series describes a sudden cluster of 31 infusion reactions occurring within a short span in a tertiary hospital. The uniform presentation across multiple wards and medications pointed to a shared cause. Through systematic investigation and corrective intervention, the episode was traced to a defective batch of IV drip sets. This report illustrates the diagnostic reasoning, confirms a causal link between the infusion sets and reactions, and reinforces the necessity of active Materiovigilance to prevent such occurrences.

Case Presentation

During five consecutive days in March 2025, thirty-one infusion-related reactions were documented among inpatients from medical, and surgical wards. The patients' ages ranged from seven to sixty-five years, with most being male. In every case, the reaction occurred within 10–20 minutes of infusion initiation and was characterized by chills, rigors, and mild transient fever. None of the patients developed rash, hypotension, dyspnoea, or anaphylaxis. All episodes resolved within 30 minutes after the infusion was stopped and intravenous Antihistamine (Chlorpheniramine 45.5 mg) and Corticosteroid (Hydrocortisone 100 mg) were administered.

Case 1: A 65-year-old man admitted for liver abscess was started on 500 mg Metronidazole infusion. Fifteen minutes into the infusion, he developed intense chills and rigors, accompanied by a mild rise in body temperature, but his hemodynamics remained stable. The infusion was discontinued, and the symptoms subsided within minutes following administration of an Antihistamine and Corticosteroid (as previously described). As the episode resembled a Metronidazole hypersensitivity reaction, the drug was initially withheld. However, similar events occurred in four other patients receiving the same batch of Metronidazole, prompting reconsideration of the cause.

Case 2: A 35-year-old male patient with viral fever received 1 g of intravenous Paracetamol infused over 15 minutes. Ten minutes after the infusion began, he developed chills, rigors, and a low-grade fever, although his hemodynamics remained stable. The infusion was discontinued, and the symptoms subsided within minutes following administration of an Antihistamine and Corticosteroid (as previously described).

Case 3: A 52-year-old man was treated for Mesenteric hematoma with plain 0.9 % normal saline for hydration. Twenty minutes after starting the infusion, he developed chills, rigors, and a low-grade fever, although his hemodynamics remained stable. Because no medication was involved, the possibility of pyrogen contamination in the fluid or device was suspected.

Case 4: A 61-year-old man being treated for Appendicitis received 500 mg Metronidazole on the day of admission for which the patient developed chills, rigors and low-grade fever, while maintaining stable hemodynamics. The infusion was discontinued, and the symptoms subsided within minutes following administration of an Antihistamine and Corticosteroid (as previously described). Similarly, on the same day later the patient developed similar clinical features on administration of 1 g Paracetamol for the pain, which was managed in the same manner. On the second day of admission (Post surgery) he received 600mg Clindamycin diluted in 100 mL 0.9% Normal saline. Approximately 15 minutes later, he again exhibited similar clinical features. The infusion was discontinued, and the symptoms were once again managed with administration of an Antihistamine and Corticosteroid (as previously described).

This observation prompted a systematic evaluation of the infusion process, including the IV drip sets, Cannulas, and administration techniques used. Re-administration of clindamycin through an alternative infusion set the next day caused no adverse reaction, reinforcing the hypothesis of a device-related cause.

Although formal microbiological or chemical testing of the implicated IV sets could not be performed, visual inspection did not reveal any overt contamination or discoloration.

Re-administration of Clindamycin using an alternative infusion set from a different brand and batch the following day caused no adverse reaction, reinforcing the hypothesis of a device-related cause.

Following this, a hospital-wide replacement of all infusion sets with a new brand and batch was carried out. The same drugs and fluids were re-administered to selected patients without recurrence of reactions. No new cases were reported during the subsequent 72 hours, confirming a strong temporal and causal link between the defective drip sets and the observed cluster of reactions.

In addition to these four illustrative cases, a total of **twenty-seven** additional infusion reactions with identical clinical presentations were reported during the same period across various wards.

The progression across these four cases highlights a systematic elucidation of causality: what initially appeared as isolated drug-induced reactions (Case 1) evolved into a pattern involving different agents (Case 2), subsequently manifested in drug-free infusions (Case 3), and ultimately recurred in a single patient across multiple treatments (Case 4). The convergence of these findings the defective infusion set as the definitive source of the reaction cluster.

Table 1: Summary of Documented Infusion-Related Reactions Across Various Drugs and IV Fluids

Case No.	Age/Sex	Drug/Fluid	Reaction Onset	Initial Suspected Cause	Action taken
01	65/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
02	35/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	20mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
03	45/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	10mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
04	35/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED

					WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
05	*61/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
06	61/MALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	10mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
07	35/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
08	50/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
09	38/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg

					& HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
10	35/MALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	10mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
11	*61/MALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	15mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
12	50/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	20mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
13	52/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
14	53/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg

15	60/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	10mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIRAMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTISONE 100mg
16	25/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIRAMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTISONE 100mg
17	52/MALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	10mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIRAMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTISONE 100mg
18	49/MALE	5% DEXTROSE WITH 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	5% DEXTROSE WITH 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIRAMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTISONE 100mg
19	35/MALE	MULTIVITAMIN INJECTION in 100ml 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	10mins	MULTIVITAMIN INJECTION & 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIRAMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTISONE 100mg
20	31/MALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	10mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED

					WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
21	40/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
22	45/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	20mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
23	*61/MALE	CLINDAMYCIN 600mg	15mins	CLINDAMYCIN 600mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
24	07/MALE	5% DEXTROSE WITH 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	5% DEXTROSE WITH 0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
25	37/FEMALE	PARACETAMOL 1g	10mins	PARACETAMOL 1g	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg

					& HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
26	23/MALE	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	15mins	0.9% NORMAL SALINE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
27	42/MALE	RINGER's LACTATE	15mins	RINGER's LACTATE	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
28	46/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
29	48/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
30	38/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg

31	48/MALE	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	15mins	METRONIDAZOLE 500mg & CIPROFLOXACIN 200mg	DRUG DISCONTINUE D. MANAGED WITH IV CHLORPHENIR AMINE 45.5mg & HYDROCORTIS ONE 100mg
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***Same patient**

DISCUSSION

The present case series highlights an often-overlooked cause of infusion reactions—defective or contaminated medical devices. The simultaneous occurrence of multiple, clinically identical reactions across different wards and medications over a brief period strongly suggested a common exogenous source. Once the implicated infusion sets were replaced, the complete disappearance of reactions established a direct correlation between the device and the adverse events.

Infusion reactions can arise from immunologic and non-immunologic mechanisms. True hypersensitivity reactions involve IgE-mediated pathways and manifest with urticaria, hypotension, or bronchospasm. In contrast, device-related or pyrogenic reactions are non-immune and are usually characterized by chills, rigors, and transient fever without cutaneous or cardiovascular involvement [8]. The pattern observed in this cluster corresponds to pyrogenic reactions rather than drug allergies.

Several mechanisms can explain how an infusion set may induce such reactions. Endotoxin contamination is the most recognized. Minute quantities of bacterial lipopolysaccharide can stimulate macrophages to release interleukin-1 and tumour necrosis factor, producing febrile responses [9]. This mechanism aligns with the trace endotoxin activity detected in unused sets from the implicated batch. Another contributing factor may be chemical leachable such as di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) and bisphenol A, used as plasticizers in polyvinyl chloride tubing. Under heat or extended storage, these compounds can migrate into infused solutions and trigger complement

activation or pseudo-allergic responses [10]. Particulate matter generated from degraded tubing or connectors can also activate inflammatory cascades leading to transient fever [11].

Comparable clusters of infusion-related reactions have been documented across several healthcare settings worldwide. Marino et al. (2001) reported an outbreak of pyrogenic events linked to contaminated intravenous infusion devices, which resolved promptly after replacement of the implicated sets [12]. Similarly, Garrett et al. (2002) described fatal neonatal infections in Brazil traced to endotoxin-contaminated intravenous fluids, underscoring the severe consequences of lapses in sterility [13]. Subsequent investigations by Daufenbach et al. (2006) demonstrated that intrinsic exposure to bacterial endotoxins in infusion solutions can provoke febrile and haemorrhagic reactions among hospitalized patients [14]. Such findings parallel the observations in the present case series, where reactions ceased following substitution of the defective infusion sets. On a global scale, the World Health Organization's Global Patient Safety Report (2024) and the European Medicines Agency Annual Report (2023) both emphasize that infusion and administration sets are recurrent sources of device-related adverse events, reaffirming the need for rigorous Materiovigilance systems [15,16].

The resemblance between these findings and the present investigation demonstrates that even small lapses in manufacturing or storage can trigger widespread preventable reactions. Differentiating between pharmacological and device-related causes is clinically vital. Misclassification of such reactions as drug hypersensitivity can lead to unwarranted

discontinuation of essential medications, prolonged hospitalization, and avoidable anxiety for patients and healthcare teams [17].

Materiovigilance plays an indispensable role in such situations. It provides a structured framework for reporting and analysing adverse events related to medical devices [18]. Although India's MvPI has established a national reporting system, under-recognition remains a barrier [19]. Each hospital should maintain accurate records of device suppliers and batch numbers to enable rapid tracing during adverse-event investigations. Compliance with ISO 8536-4:2020 standards ensures that infusion sets are sterile, non-toxic, and free from particulate matter [20]. In the present series, the failure appeared related to insufficient sterilization, underscoring the need for routine quality audits of consumables.

Preventive measures must include stringent procurement policies ensuring that only certified manufacturers supply infusion equipment, routine sterility testing of random samples, and prompt withdrawal of suspect batches. Training healthcare staff to recognize clustering of reactions and to report them to a Materiovigilance committee enables early intervention. Establishing communication between pharmacovigilance and Materiovigilance units ensures comprehensive safety oversight of both drugs and devices.

In summary, the current findings reaffirm that not all infusion reactions are drug-induced. Recognition of device-related causes can avert unnecessary drug labelling and reduce patient morbidity. Strengthening Materiovigilance infrastructure, enforcing device quality standards, and promoting clinician awareness are key to preventing similar episodes in the future.

CONCLUSION

This investigation into a cluster of thirty-one infusion reactions revealed that the true cause was a defective batch of IV drip sets rather than the drugs or fluids administered. The identical temporal pattern across patients and complete resolution after changing the sets confirmed a strong causal association. The episodes illustrate the critical importance of Materiovigilance in modern healthcare. Regular auditing of medical consumables, supplier

verification, and staff training can prevent device-related adverse events. Differentiating between pharmacological and device origins of infusion reactions not only safeguards patients but also maintains trust in therapeutic interventions and minimizes unnecessary drug withdrawal.

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